

Supplementary material

Sensitivity analysis: Less informative priors for FOI

Supplementary Table 1. Parameter estimates from the age-varying FOI reverse catalytic model. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha and the cut-off were allowed to vary across settings. Waning was held across all studies and strains. Less informative priors were used for FOI, Normal $\sim (0.3,0.5)$.

Strain	First Author	FOI	Alpha	Cut-off	Waning	WAIC	LOO
HCoV-229E	Shao	1.03 (0.58 - 1.76)	1.08 (0.42 - 1.9)	11.14 (0.48 - 19.62)	1.08 (0.61 - 1.68)	536.4 (SE: 99.6)	546.0 (SE: 100.6)
	Zhou	3.22 (1.95 - 4.85)	2.12 (1.72 - 2.58)	3.17 (2.02 - 4.51)			
	Cavallaro	0.46 (0.20 - 1.49)	0.74 (0.23 - 1.32)	5.69 (0.30 - 19.2)			
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.09 (0.04 - 0.16)	2.44 (1.61 - 3.63)	17.38 (9.63 - 19.87)	1.08 (0.61 - 1.68)	536.4 (SE: 99.6)	546.0 (SE: 100.6)
	Zhou	1.65 (1.00 - 2.54)	2.12 (1.72 - 2.58)	3.17 (2.02 - 4.51)			
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	1.80 (1.09 - 2.77)	2.12 (1.72 - 2.58)	3.17 (2.02 - 4.51)	1.08 (0.61 - 1.68)	536.4 (SE: 99.6)	546.0 (SE: 100.6)
	Monto	0.30 (0.14 - 0.96)	0.74 (0.23 - 1.32)	5.69 (0.30 - 19.2)			
	Sarateanu	0.73 (0.4 - 1.17)	2.63 (2.24 - 3.10)	12.57 (7.72 - 17.71)			
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	1.36 (0.83 - 2.1)	2.12 (1.72 - 2.58)	3.17 (2.02 - 4.51)	1.08 (0.61 - 1.68)	536.4 (SE: 99.6)	546.0 (SE: 100.6)
	Shao	1.11 (0.62 - 1.9)	1.08 (0.42 - 1.90)	11.14 (0.48 - 19.62)			

Supplementary Figure 1. Reverse catalytic model with age-varying FOI. The points are the observed proportion of seropositive individuals from each study (with confidence intervals). The lines are the seroprevalence curves from the model, with shaded 95% credible intervals. Less informative priors were used for FOI [Normal $\sim$ (0.3,0.5)].

Sensitivity analysis: Waning estimated by strain

Supplementary Table 2. Parameter estimates from the age-varying FOI reverse catalytic model. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha and the cut-off were allowed to vary across settings. Waning was allowed to vary by strain.

Strain	First Author	FOI	Alpha	Waning	Cut-off	WAIC	LOO
HCoV-229E	Shao	0.37 (0.23 - 0.63)	0.85 (0.37 - 1.76)	0.24 (0.1 - 0.52)	10.33 (0.51 - 19.57)	545.0 (SE: 99.8)	560.4 (SE 100.9)
	Zhou	0.9 (0.48 - 1.68)	1.8 (0.94 - 2.95)		2.4 (0.74 - 12.14)		
	Cavallaro	0.09 (0.04 - 0.25)	0.79 (0.41 - 1.35)		10.6 (0.41 - 19.44)		
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.03 (0.01 - 0.09)	2.33 (1.5 - 3.53)	0.37 (0.15 - 1.01)	16.89 (8.39 - 19.84)	545.0 (SE: 99.8)	560.4 (SE 100.9)
	Zhou	0.67 (0.35 - 1.56)	1.8 (0.94 - 2.95)		2.4 (0.74 - 12.14)		
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.85 (0.43 - 1.66)	1.8 (0.94 - 2.95)	0.44 (0.2 - 0.94)	2.4 (0.74 - 12.14)		
	Monto	0.11 (0.05 - 0.27)	0.79 (0.41 - 1.35)		10.6 (0.41 - 19.44)		
	Sarateanu	0.3 (0.15 - 0.64)	2.6 (2.17 - 3.09)		11.14 (7.56 - 16.29)		
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.62 (0.33 - 1.14)	1.8 (0.94 - 2.95)	0.41 (0.18 - 0.87)	2.4 (0.74 - 12.14)	545.0 (SE: 99.8)	560.4 (SE 100.9)
	Shao	0.53 (0.31 - 0.97)	0.85 (0.37 - 1.76)		10.33 (0.51 - 19.57)		

Sensitivity analysis: Alpha and cut-off jointly estimated by study

Supplementary Table 3. Parameter estimates from the age-varying FOI reverse catalytic model. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha, cut-off and waning was held across all studies and strains.

Strain	First Author	FOI	Alpha	Waning	Cut-off	WAIC	LOO
HCoV-229E	Shao	0.45 (0.31 - 0.65)	1.93 (1.69 - 2.19)	0.45 (0.32 - 0.64)	8.49 (7.52 - 9.94)	622.1 (SE: 103.3)	632.5 (SE: 105.6)
	Zhou	1.52 (1.12 - 2.12)					
	Cavallaro	0.08 (0.06 - 0.12)					
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.04 (0.03 - 0.06)					
	Zhou	0.81 (0.61 - 1.1)					
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.88 (0.67 - 1.19)					
	Monto	0.06 (0.04 - 0.08)					
	Sarateanu	0.39 (0.29 - 0.52)					
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.68 (0.51 - 0.91)					
	Shao	0.47 (0.32 - 0.69)					

Supplementary Figure 2. Reverse catalytic model with age-varying FOI. The points are the observed proportion of seropositive individuals from each study (with confidence intervals). The lines are the seroprevalence curves from the model, with shaded 95% credible intervals. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha, cut-off and waning was held across all studies and strains.

Reverse catalytic model

Supplementary Table 4. Parameter estimates from the reverse catalytic model. Waning was jointly estimated across all studies, but FOI was allowed to vary by study.

Strain	First Author	FOI	Waning	WAIC	LOO
HCoV-229E	Shao	0.26 (0.19 - 0.36)	0.13 (0.11 - 0.16)	717.2 (SE: 156.8)	713.8 (SE: 151.8)
	Zhou	0.85 (0.7 - 1.04)			
	Cavallaro	0.05 (0.03 - 0.06)			
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.02 (0.02 - 0.03)			
	Zhou	0.47 (0.39 - 0.57)			
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.51 (0.43 - 0.63)			
	Monto	0.03 (0.02 - 0.04)			
	Sarateanu	0.18 (0.16 - 0.22)			
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.39 (0.33 - 0.48)			
	Shao	0.27 (0.2 - 0.37)			

Supplementary Figure 3. Reverse catalytic model. The points are the observed proportion of seropositive individuals from each study (with confidence intervals). The lines are the seroprevalence curves from the model, with shaded 95% credible intervals.

Sensitivity analysis: Including the youngest age groups (<1 year)

Supplementary Table 5. Parameter estimates from the age-varying FOI reverse catalytic model, which includes data from the youngest age group (≤ 1 year). FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha and cut-off was allowed to vary by setting. Waning was simultaneously estimated across all studies.

Strain	First Author	FOI	Alpha	Cut-off	Waning
HCoV-229E	Shao	2.92 (2.08 - 4.01)	0.2 (0.1 - 0.35)	0.09 (0.07 - 0.14)	0.49 (0.21 - 0.78)
	Zhou	1.64 (1.04 - 2.42)	1.81 (1.06 - 2.33)	2.93 (1.85 - 7.39)	
	Cavallaro	0.18 (0.08 - 0.44)	0.8 (0.35 - 1.38)	8.43 (0.4 - 19.38)	
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.04 (0.02 - 0.07)	2.39 (1.56 - 3.58)	17.08 (9.14 - 19.85)	
	Zhou	0.89 (0.6 - 1.28)	1.81 (1.06 - 2.33)	2.93 (1.85 - 7.39)	
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.94 (0.64 - 1.37)	1.81 (1.06 - 2.33)	2.93 (1.85 - 7.39)	
	Monto	0.12 (0.05 - 0.28)	0.8 (0.35 - 1.38)	8.43 (0.4 - 19.38)	
	Sarateanu	0.33 (0.15 - 0.54)	2.62 (2.19 - 3.1)	11.36 (7.58 - 16.32)	
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.74 (0.5 - 1.06)	1.81 (1.06 - 2.33)	2.93 (1.85 - 7.39)	
	Shao	2.47 (1.73 - 3.41)	0.2 (0.1 - 0.35)	0.09 (0.07 - 0.14)	

Supplementary Figure 4. Reverse catalytic model with age-varying FOI, which includes data from the youngest age group (≤ 1 year). The points are the observed proportion of seropositive individuals from each study (with confidence intervals). The lines are the seroprevalence curves from the model, with shaded 95% credible intervals.

Sensitivity analysis: Refitting the model using data from only two strains

Supplementary Table 6. Parameter estimates from cross comparison models, which used half the data (only two strains included at once). Alpha, cut-off and waning were held across studies, whilst FOI was allowed to vary by study.

	Strain	First Author	FOI	Alpha	Cut-off	Waning
Model 1	HCoV-OC43	Zhou	1.02 (0.73 - 1.53)	2.01 (1.75 - 2.31)	8.61 (7.53 - 10.13)	0.56 (0.38 - 0.85)
		Monto	0.06 (0.04 - 0.1)			
		Sarateanu	0.46 (0.32 - 0.69)			
	HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.79 (0.56 - 1.16)			
		Shao	0.54 (0.35 - 0.84)			
Model 2	HCoV-229E	Shao	0.34 (0.22 - 0.55)	1.45 (0.5 - 1.96)	16.41 (1.29 - 19.81)	0.23 (0.07 - 0.42)
		Zhou	1.03 (0.74 - 1.57)			
		Cavallaro	0.06 (0.04 - 0.1)			
	HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.03 (0.02 - 0.05)			
		Zhou	0.57 (0.42 - 0.84)			
Model 3	HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.52 (0.39 - 0.76)	1.05 (0.42 - 1.63)	7.86 (0.48 - 19.45)	0.19 (0.07 - 0.39)
		Shao	0.33 (0.22 - 0.52)			
	HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.03 (0.02 - 0.05)			
		Zhou	0.61 (0.46 - 0.9)			
Model 4	HCoV-NL63	Zhou	0.54 (0.4 - 0.81)	1.28 (0.68 - 1.86)	13.01 (0.77 - 19.72)	0.24 (0.12 - 0.5)
		Shao	0.35 (0.23 - 0.55)			

	HCoV-229E	Shao	0.35 (0.23 - 0.53)			
		Zhou	1.16 (0.82 - 1.83)			
		Cavallaro	0.07 (0.04 - 0.11)			
Model 5	HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.97 (0.67 - 1.58)	2.1 (1.82 - 2.41)	8.5 (7.52 - 9.93)	0.54 (0.35 - 0.92)
		Monto	0.06 (0.04 - 0.1)			
		Sarateanu	0.43 (0.29 - 0.72)			
	HCoV-HKU1	Chan	0.05 (0.03 - 0.08)			
		Zhou	0.89 (0.62 - 1.45)			
Model 6	HCoV-OC43	Zhou	0.91 (0.64 - 1.35)	2.07 (1.8 - 2.37)	8.46 (7.52 - 9.95)	0.5 (0.32 - 0.76)
		Monto	0.06 (0.04 - 0.09)			
		Sarateanu	0.4 (0.27 - 0.6)			
	HCoV-229E	Shao	0.47 (0.31 - 0.72)			
		Zhou	1.58 (1.09 - 2.4)			
		Cavallaro	0.09 (0.05 - 0.14)			

Sensitivity analysis: Waning estimated by assay

Supplementary Table 7. Parameter estimates from the age-varying FOI reverse catalytic model. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha and the cut-off were allowed to vary across settings. Waning was allowed to vary by serological assay.

Strain	First Author	Assay	FOI	Alpha	Waning	Cut-off	WAIC	LOO
HCoV-229E	Shao	ELISA (IgG)	0.47 (0.27 - 0.94)	0.89 (0.33 - 1.88)	0.38 (0.11 - 1.06)	10.2 (0.46 - 19.56)	545.1 (SE: 99.9)	560.4 (SE: 101.0)
	Zhou	IFA (IgG)	0.9 (0.66 - 1.26)	0.78 (0.45 - 2.03)	0.13 (0.07 - 0.33)	8.87 (0.42 - 18.93)		
	Cavallaro	Neutralisation	0.26 (0.02 - 1.19)	0.82 (0.47 - 1.66)	0.78 (0.02 - 3.93)	11.22 (0.49 - 19.47)		
HCoV-HKU1	Chan	ELISA (IgG)	0.03 (0.01 - 0.09)	2.33 (1.46 - 3.53)	0.38 (0.11 - 1.06)	16.86 (7.85 - 19.84)		
	Zhou	IFA (IgG)	0.52 (0.37 - 0.7)	0.78 (0.45 - 2.03)	0.13 (0.07 - 0.33)	8.87 (0.42 - 18.93)		
HCoV-OC43	Zhou	IFA (IgG)	0.57 (0.4 - 0.76)	0.78 (0.45 - 2.03)	0.13 (0.07 - 0.33)	8.87 (0.42 - 18.93)		
	Monto	CF or HI ^a	0.21 (0.07 - 0.55)	0.82 (0.47 - 1.66)	0.93 (0.3 - 2.27)	11.22 (0.49 - 19.47)		
	Sarateanu	HI	0.62 (0.2 - 1.5)	2.66 (2.25 - 3.13)	0.93 (0.3 - 2.27)	12.23 (7.68 - 17.67)		
HCoV-NL63	Zhou	IFA (IgG)	0.44 (0.31 - 0.59)	0.78 (0.45 - 2.03)	0.13 (0.07 - 0.33)	8.87 (0.42 - 18.93)		
	Shao	ELISA (IgG)	0.49 (0.27 - 1)	0.89 (0.33 - 1.88)	0.38 (0.11 - 1.06)	10.2 (0.46 - 19.56)		

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA), immunofluorescence assays (IFA), complement fixation (CF), hemagglutination inhibition assays (HI). ^aFor the purposes of this analysis, this was treated as HI.

Supplementary Figure 5. Reverse catalytic model with age-varying FOI. The points are the observed proportion of seropositive individuals from each study (with confidence intervals). The lines are the seroprevalence curves from the model, with shaded 95% credible intervals. FOI was allowed to vary by study, whilst alpha and cut-off were allowed to vary by setting, and waning varied by assay.